

Name of Field Station	Stengl Lost Pines Biological Field Station (SLP)
Ownership	University of Texas at Austin. Donated to UT in 1991 by Dr. Lorraine "Casey" Stengl.
Website	https://bfl.utexas.edu/stengl/
Contact phone number	(512) 237-9656
Mailing address	405 Old Antioch Road, Smithville TX 78957
State, County	Texas, Bastrop County
Contact persons	Steven Gibson, Dr L. Gilbert, Dr R. Plowes
Mission Statement	To innovate and successfully prepare students through field-based studies of diverse natural systems, and to promote world-changing discoveries and improve our world through a better understanding of these systems.
Setting	SLP is situated in the Lost Pines habitat of Bastrop County, an isolated population of flora and fauna typically found farther east. These species, along with some of those typically found in Central Texas, provide unique research and powerful teaching opportunities.
Area	581 acres
Date established	Formal establishment, September 1991
Landuse history	Limited areas were used for timber harvest and row crops (early 1900's), Limited cattle grazing and isolated timber clearing (1950's and 1960's). The original 208 acre block has had little manipulation since early 1960's. The north 373 acre block (acquired 2016) saw cattle grazing through 2015 and small patches of forest cleared in the 1990's and 2000's.
Lat/long	30.087359°N, -97.17374°W
Elevation	133 – 155 m a.s.l.
Ecoregion	SLP sits near the intersection of the Post Oak Savannah and Blackland Prairie ecoregions.
Vegetation	Forest: Mixed coniferous and hardwoods (<i>Pinus taeda</i> , <i>Juniperus virginiana</i> , <i>Quercus stellata</i> , <i>Quercus marylandica</i> , <i>Carya texana</i> trees). Native prairies and savannah. (<i>Paspalum</i> , <i>Agrostus</i> , <i>Dicanthium</i> , <i>Andropogon</i> , <i>Schizachyrium</i> grasses, and seasonal forbs). Riparian woodland (<i>Ulmus americana</i> , <i>Quercus nigra</i> , <i>Plantanus occidentalis</i> , <i>Prunus caroliniana</i> , <i>Morus nigra</i> , <i>Pinus taeda</i> trees).
Soil types, USDA	Generally, a sandy surface layer of varying depth with clay pan beneath. Meadows and Prairies: AfC Axtell fine sandy loam 1-5% slopes CfB Crockett fine sandy loam 1-3% slopes CsC2 Crockett soils 2-5% slopes, eroded DeC Demona loamy fine sand, somewhat poorly drained variant DoB Dougherty loamy fine sand, 3-8% slopes MaB Mabank loam, 1-3% slopes

	<p>WsA Wilson clay loam, 0-1% slopes WsB Wilson clay loam, 1-3% slopes</p> <p>Forest: AfC Axtell fine sandy loam 1-5% slopes AfC2 Axtell fine sandy loam 2-5% slopes, eroded CsD3 Crockett soils 3-8% slopes, severely eroded CfB Crockett fine sandy loam 1-3% slopes DeC Demona loamy fine sand, somewhat poorly drained variant TfB Tabor fine sandy loam, 0-1% slopes</p> <p>Riparian: AtD Axtell-Tabor complex 1-8% slopes TfB Tabor fine sandy loam, 0-1% slopes</p>
Weather records	Onsite weather station KTXSMITH12 since Jan 2015. Refer to Austin Bergstrom International Airport for weather records (41 km from SLP) for long term weather data.
Rainfall	Average yearly rainfall is near 38 inches. Extremes at Austin Mabry (61 km west of SLP), since 1856, vary from 11.52 inches low in 1954 to 64.68 inches high in 1919.
Summer temperatures	Summer daytime temperatures hot, with highs over 90F more than 107 days per year. Typically 20-30 days per year over 100F.
Winter temperatures	Av 29 freezing days per year, between late November and early March.